

Some heterocycles from dehydro-L-ascorbic acid and dehydro-D-isoascorbic acid

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Reaction of *D-erythro*-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-phenylhydrazine **1** with *p*-sulfamylphenylhydrazine gives the 3-*p*-sulfamylphenylhydrazine **2**, which upon treatment with hydrazine hydrate or CuCl₂ affords pyrazolinedione **4** or 3,6-anhydro derivative **6**, respectively. Condensation of the aldehyde **8** with thiosemicarbazide or hydroxylamine produces 3-carboxaldehydethiosemicarbazone **12** or hydroxyiminomethyl derivative **9**, which reacts with BzCl to give the bicyclic **11**. Reaction of the furotriazole **14** with hydrazine hydrate gives carboxylic acid hydrazide **15** which upon treatment with some carbonyl compounds or CS₂ yields acylhydrazones **6-20**, **22** or binuclear heterocycle **27**. Acetylation of **2**, **4** and **9** gives the corresponding acetylated derivatives **3**, **5** and **10**, while that of **12**, **16**, **19**, **20** and **22** produces the corresponding cyclized derivatives **13**, **23-26**.

Some of the 4,5-pyrazolinediones are used as potential drugs¹. This attracted our attention to the synthesis of some pyrazolinediones having the active part of sulfanilamide drugs and a carbohydrate moiety on the ring. Thus, when *D-erythro*-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-phenylhydrazine **1** was treated with *p*-sulfamylphenylhydrazine, it gave the *D-erythro*-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-phenylhydrazine-3-*p*-sulfamylphenylhydrazine **2**. Acetylation of **2** with acetic anhydride and pyridine afforded the corresponding 5,6-di-*O*-acetyl derivative **3**. Boiling **2** with hydrazine hydrate and acidification afforded 1-*p*-sulfamylphenyl-3-(*D-erythro*-glycerol-1-yl)-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-phenylhydrazine **4**. Acetylation of **4** with boiling acetic anhydride afforded the corresponding triacetate **5**. Mild oxidation of **2** with CuCl₂ gave 3,6-anhydro-3-*p*-sulfamylphenylazo-2-oxo-*D*-lyxo-1,4-lactone-2-phenylhydrazine **6**.

D-erythro-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-phenylhydrazine **1** afforded 3-carboxaldehyde-1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-phenylhydrazine² **8**. Reaction of the aldehyde **8** with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate afforded 3-hydroxyiminomethyl-1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-phenylhydrazine (**9**). Acetylation of **9** with boiling acetic anhydride gave 3-acetoxyiminomethyl-1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-phenylhydrazine **10**. On the other hand, treatment of **9** with benzoyl chloride and pyridine for long period afforded 6,7-dihydro-7-oxo-6-*p*-nitrophenyl-2-phenyl-2*H*-pyrazolo[4,3-*d*]-1,2,3-triazine **11**. Condensation of the formyl derivative **8** with thiosemicarbazide afforded 3-carboxaldehyde-1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-phenylhydrazine-3-thiosemicarbazone **12**. Boiling **12** with acetic anhydride afforded 3-(2-acetamido-4-acetyl-2,1,3,4-thiadiazolin-5-yl)-1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-phenylhydrazine **13**.

Sodium metaperiodate oxidation of 1-*p*-nitrophenyl-3-(*D-erythro*-glycerol-1-yl)-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-phenylhy-

Note

In continuation of the work on the synthesis of nitrogen heterocycles from L-ascorbic acid derivatives and its analogs, we found it interesting to synthesize binuclear heterocycles, namely, oxadiazolotriazoles. Thus, treatment of 4*H*-furo[3,4-*d*]-1,2,3-triazol-4-one-2-phenyl-2,6-dihydro-6-(1,2-diacetoxyethyl)³ **14** with hydrazine hydrate in methanol resulted in deacetylation along with opening of the lactone ring to afford 2-phenyl-4-(*L*-*threo*-glycer-1-yl)-1,2,3-triazole-5-carboxylic acid hydrazide **15**. Condensation of **15** with benzaldehyde, *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde or acetophenone afforded the corresponding acylhydrazones **16-20**. Similarly, condensation of **15** with 3-carboxaldehyde-1-phenyl-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-phenylhydrazone⁴ **21** afforded the corresponding acylhydrazone **22**. Cyclization of **16**, **19**, **20** and **22** with boiling acetic anhydride afforded the desired oxadiazolotriazoles **23-26**. Treatment of **15** with carbon

disulfide in pyridine gave 2-phenyl-5-(1,3,4-oxadiazolin-2-thio-5-yl)-4-(*L*-*threo*-glycer-1-yl)-1,2,3-triazole **27**.

Experimental

M.p.s. were recorded on a Total (Buchi) apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 580 B spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV 160A spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Microanalysis was performed at Microanalytical Unit, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt.

Compound 2 : A solution of **1** (4.2 mmol) in ethanol (40 ml) was refluxed for 6 h with *p*-sulfamylphenylhydrazine (5.3 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) in the presence of a few drops of acetic acid. The solid that separated on cooling was washed with ethanol, dried (15 g, 82%) and crystal-

lized from ethanol as red needles, m.p. 249–250° (Found : C, 50.2; H, 4.4; N, 16.6. $C_{18}H_{19}N_5SO_6$ calcd. for : C, 49.88; H, 4.42; N, 16.16%); ν_{\max} 3400 (OH), 3240 (NH), 1720 cm^{-1} (lactone C=O).

Compound 3 : A solution of **2** (0.23 mmol) in pyridine (10 ml) was treated with Ac_2O (10 ml). The mixture was left overnight at room temperature, then poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid was washed with water and ethanol, dried (0.1 g, 84%) and crystallized from ethanol as red needles, m.p. 141–143°.

Compound 4 : A solution of **2** (1.15 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (1 ml) for 1 h, then cooled and acidified with acetic acid. The separated solid was washed successively with water, ethanol and ether, dried (0.39 g, 78%) and crystallized from ethanol as orange needles, m.p. 265–267° (Found : C, 49.7; H, 4.8; N, 16.4. $C_{18}H_{19}N_5SO_6$ calcd. for : C, 49.88; H, 4.4; N, 16.16%); ν_{\max} 3450 (OH), 3300, 3200 (NH), 1660 cm^{-1} (OCN); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 268, 410 nm (log ϵ 4.35, 4.33); λ_{\min} 307 (log ϵ 3.64).

Compound 5 : A suspension of **4** (0.23 mmol) in acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 1 h, and then cooled. The mixture was poured onto crushed ice, and the separated solid was washed with water and ethanol, dried (1.1 g, 85%) and crystallized from ethanol as orange needles, m.p. 204–205°.

Compound 6 : A suspension of **2** (0.23 mmol) in a solution of cupric chloride (10%) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 15 min. Hot water (5 ml) was then added and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol, dried (70 mg, 70.5%) and crystallized from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 225–226° (Found : C, 50.0; H, 4.2; N, 16.4. $C_{18}H_{17}N_5SO_6$ calcd. for : C, 50.12; H, 3.96; N, 16.27%); ν_{\max} 3400 (OH), 3220 (NH), 1740 cm^{-1} (lactone C=O); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 262, 243, 280, 364 nm (log ϵ 2.50, 2.56, 2.60, 2.19); λ_{\min} 232, 259, 317 nm (log ϵ 2.42, 2.39, 2.19).

Compound 9 : A solution of **8** (5 mmol) in ethanol (30 ml) was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (10 mmol), sodium acetate (10 mmol) and acetic acid (5 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 2 h and concentrated to a small volume. Hot water (10 ml) was then added and the solid that separated was washed with water and ethanol, dried (1.5 g, 85%) and crystallized from chloroform-ethanol mixture (1 : 1, v/v) as orange needles, m.p. 265–267° (Found : C, 54.9; H, 3.6; N, 23.5. $C_{16}H_{12}N_6O_4$ calcd. for : C, 54.54; H, 3.43; N, 23.86%); ν_{\max} 3260 (OH), 1664 (OCN), 1592 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Compound 10 : A suspension of **9** (1.1 mmol) in Ac_2O

(10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The mixture was then cooled and poured onto crushed ice and the solid that separated was washed with water and ethanol, dried (0.35 g, 78%) and crystallized from chloroform-ethanol mixture (1 : 1, v/v) as orange needles, m.p. 210–212°.

Compound 11 : A solution of **9** (1.1 mmol) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was treated with benzoyl chloride (2 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 8 days at room temperature. It was then poured onto crushed ice and the solid that separated was washed successively with water, ethanol and ether, dried (0.21 g, 57%) and crystallized from chloroform-ethanol mixture (1 : 1, v/v) as red needles, m.p. 233–235° (Found : C, 57.8; H, 3.4; N, 25.5. $C_{16}H_{10}N_6O_3$ calcd. for : C, 57.48; H, 3.02; N, 25.14%); ν_{\max} 1659 (OCN), 1590 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.07 (1H, s, H-4), 7.2–8.1 (9H, m, ArH).

Compound 12 : A solution of **8** (5 mmol) in ethanol (30 ml) was treated with thiosemicarbazide (6 mmol) and acetic acid (5 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h, then cooled and poured onto crushed ice. The separated solid was washed successively with water and ethanol, dried (1.7 g, 83%) and crystallized from chloroform-ethanol mixture (1 : 1, v/v) as red needles, m.p. 269–270° (Found : C, 50.0; H, 3.8; N, 27.0. $C_{17}H_{14}N_8SO_3$ calcd. for : C, 49.75; H, 3.44; N, 27.31%); ν_{\max} 3223, 3144 (NH), 1659 (OCN), 1594 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Compound 13 : A suspension of **12** (2.4 mmol) in Ac_2O (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and poured onto crushed ice. The separated solid was washed with water and ethanol, dried (1.1 g, 91%) and crystallized from chloroform-ethanol mixture (1 : 1, v/v) as orange needles, m.p. 284–285° (Found : C, 50.7; H, 3.3; N, 22.4. $C_{21}H_{18}N_8SO_5$ calcd. for : C, 51.01; H, 3.67; N, 22.66%); ν_{\max} 3161 (NH), 1695 (OCN), 1618 ($NCOCH_3$), 1591 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ ($DMSO-d_6$) 2.1 (3H, s, $NHAc$), 2.27 (3H, s, NAC), 6.9 (1H, s, H-5), 7.3–8.05 (9H, m, ArH), 8.3 (1H, s, NH), 11.87 (1H, s, NH).

Compound 15 : A solution of **14** (2.9 mmol) in methanol (50 ml) was treated with hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) and kept overnight at room temperature. The solution was then concentrated to small volume at diminished pressure and the solid that separated was washed with methanol, dried (0.65 g, 76%) and crystallized from ethanol as colorless needles, m.p. 155–157° (Found : C, 48.82; H, 5.36; N, 24.23. $C_{12}H_{15}N_5O_4$ calcd. for : C, 49.14; H, 5.16; N, 23.88%); ν_{\max} 3450 (OH), 1640 cm^{-1} (OCN).

Compounds 16–20, 22 : A solution of **15** (0.85 mmol) in ethanol (30 ml) was treated with benzaldehyde, o-

Note

chlorobenzaldehyde, *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, acetophenone, or the aldehyde **21** (0.85 mmol) and few drops of acetic acid. The mixture was refluxed for 2 h, then allowed to cool to room temperature. The products were washed with ethanol and dried (yields 74–85%); ν_{\max} 3400–3438 (OH), 3240–3300 (NH), 1639–1683 (OCN), 1590–1608 cm^{-1} (C=N); **16**, m.p. 104–106° (Found : C, 60.2; H, 4.6; N, 18.0. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 59.83; H, 5.02; N, 18.36%); **17**, 200–202°; **18**, 169–170°; **19**, 179–180°; **20**, 105–106°; **22**, 254–255° (Found : C, 59.5; H, 4.7; N, 22.0. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_9\text{O}_5$ calcd. for : C, 59.25; H, 4.44; N, 22.21%).

Compounds 23–26 : Suspension of acylhydrazone (**16**, **19**, **20** or **22**) (0.15 g) in Ac_2O (10 ml) was boiled under reflux for 90 min. The mixture was poured onto crushed ice and the product was washed with water, dried (yields 67–77%); ν_{\max} 1745–1747 (ester), 1666–1683 cm^{-1} (OCN); δ (CDCl_3) 1.86–2.13 (s, 3×OAc), 2.14–2.35 (s, NAc), 4.18–3.33 (m, H-3), 5.7–5.8 (m, H-2), 6.53–6.93 (d, H-1), 7.1–8.3 (m, ArH), 10–13.72 (1H, s, CH within ArH); **23**, syrup (Found : C, 58.7; H, 4.4; N, 12.5. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_5\text{O}_8$ calcd.

for : C, 59.01, H, 4.95; N, 12.75%); **24**, m.p. 66–67°; **25**, syrup; **26**, m.p. 143–144°

Compound 27 : A solution of **15** (0.85 mmol) in pyridine (10 ml) was treated with carbon disulfide (5 ml), and kept overnight at room temperature. The mixture was then poured onto crushed ice and the solid that separated was washed with water, dried (0.15 g, 63%) and crystallized from benzene-methanol mixture (1 : 1, v/v) as yellowish needles, m.p. 130–132° (Found : C, 46.2, H, 4.0; N, 20.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{SO}_4$ calcd. for : C, 46.57; H, 3.91; N, 20.89%), ν_{\max} 3355 (OH), 1630 (C=N), 1540 (CSNH), 1102 cm^{-1} (C=S).

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